

A mixed-methods study for understanding the motives of trans persons' participation in leisure-time physical activity and sport

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Abstract

The primary objective of this mixed-methods study was to identify and comprehensively understand the motives that drive trans people to engage in leisure-time physical activities and sports (LTPAS). In the quantitative phase, face-to-face surveys were administered to 155 Spanish trans persons [64 women (TW), 84 men (TM), and 7 non-conforming binary gender participants (NBG)]. The qualitative phase included 43 semi-structured interviews (21 TW, 17 TM, and 5 NBG). The fieldwork was carried out between 2012 and 2015. The most prominent motive was “to do physical exercise” while the least important was “to enjoy competing.” TM and NBG persons expressed higher levels than TW in motives such as “to reaffirm my gender identity,” “to do physical exercise,” “to enjoy doing sport,” and “to increase my musculature.” Additional extrinsic (“appearance and body image”) and intrinsic motives (“pleasure of body exertion”) were identified in the qualitative phase. Extrinsic and the relationship between intrinsic-extrinsic motives highlight the importance of gender reaffirming embodiment among the participants. These findings have the potential to raise awareness and sensitize professionals, policymakers, and society at large to promote greater involvement and more fulfilling experiences for trans persons in LTPAS.

Keywords: exercise, intrinsic motives, extrinsic motives, mix-methods, transgender.

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Although the positive biological and psychosocial health outcomes of leisure-time physical activity and sport (LTPAS) are widely acknowledged (Warburton et al., 2006), the social distribution of access to and satisfactory practice of LTPAS is by no means equally distributed in the general population, particularly among vulnerable social groups such as trans or transgender persons. These are people whose gender identities do not match the gender they were assigned at birth, based on their biological anatomy (Stryker, 1994).

Along with its general benefits for everybody, LTPAS is of special worth to trans people. For instance, it can complement or accelerate the effects of hormone treatment, alleviate any possible side effects (such as liquid retention, hepatic problems, blood clotting, insomnia, psychological stress or overweight), and contribute to maintaining an appropriate weight for their health (Elling-Machartzki, 2017; Schrock et al., 2005). Participating in LTPAS can also help to overcome potential mental health problems, foster wellbeing and even favor recognition and social justice in this vulnerable social group (Fredriksen-Goldsen et al., 2013; Millet et al., 2017).

Despite these benefits, trans people are often rejected or hindered from participating in LTPAS contexts. Studies have reported that trans persons' LTPAS levels are lower than those of cisgender persons (Jones et al., 2018; Muchicko et al., 2014). In Spain, López-Cañada et al. (2020) found that, despite the participation of trans persons in LTPAS before gender disclosure (GD) (opening and sharing their new gender identity) being similar to that of the general population (without differentiating cis and trans people), it becomes drastically reduced after GD in specific areas, particularly in team sports and in contexts that demand a certain amount of body exposure (i.e., swimming pools). Different reasons and barriers have

been suggested as being behind this low level of participation, such as fear of public spaces, body dissatisfaction, anxiety, discrimination and inadequate changing facilities (Hargie et al., 2017; Jones et al., 2017; Pérez-Samaniego et al., 2019).

The connection between motivation and engagement or commitment to LTPAS is of particular importance, since being motivated encourages people to do things (Ryan & Deci, 2000). The study of trans persons' motives for participating in LTPAS is thus useful in aligning professional practice with people's needs and promoting their participation, as previous studies have indicated (Teti et al., 2020).

The motives refer to reasons for action and motivation refers to the psychological processes behind the reasons for certain behavior. According to the tenets of the self-determination theory, motives are understood as dispositions or states manifested by individuals that encourage initiating or maintaining certain activities (Ryan & Deci, 2000). This theory indicates that motivated behavior is based on the satisfaction of three needs (competence, autonomy and relatedness) and distinguishes three types of motivation (intrinsic, extrinsic and amotivation). The first two types of motivation are based on internally or externally driven forces behind the reasons or goals, while the third is the absence of a driving force known as amotivation. If amotivation is the lack of an intention to act, intrinsic and extrinsic motivations are driven by the forces that impel to action. Intrinsic motivation is thus behind the motives that imply doing something because it is inherently satisfying (e.g., "to enjoy doing sport"), while extrinsic motivation is behind motives that imply doing something because it leads to an outcome driven by external forces (e.g., "to keep and improve health"). Sociologists also emphasize the fact that people's motives are understood within the cultural contexts that shape them (Voyer, 2017). Besides the psychological perspective, the sociological study of the reasons behind participating in LTPAS thus offers a

more contextualized understanding of the factors that motivate people to exercise and how they are distributed within the population (Coakley, 2012).

Most of the studies on the motives for participation in LTPAS are survey-based. This type of study, which takes great care in measuring these motives and developing the research process to achieve potential replicability, refers to a huge variety of the motives of whether or not to engage in LTPAS. The recurrent motives, such as physical competence, health and physical condition, body appearance, enjoyment and social connection, are related to participation in LTPAS and differ according to sociodemographic variables such as gender and age (Brudzynski & Ebben, 2010; Molanorouzi et al., 2015). In Spain, being fit, fun and entertainment, exercise, health, and relaxation are the main motives for participating in LTPAS (García & Llopis, 2011; Ministry of Education, Culture & Sport, 2015).

Although the above survey studies explain why people take part in LTPAS, they do not reveal the deeper reasons for their participation (i.e., the underlying meanings that shape their motives). A more holistic approach to understanding the motives and their underlying meanings is essential for those engaged in health promotion and redistribution of social benefits such as LTPAS. Only a small number of qualitative studies have addressed the study of motives from an interpretive perspective (Frühauf et al., 2022; Zhou et al., 2020), while a mixed-methods perspective with the interpretation of the meanings is difficult to find (e.g. Diehl et al., 2018).

In the particular case of trans persons' participating in LTPAS, a limited number of qualitative studies indirectly refer to the reasons behind this group's decision of (dis)engagement (Caudwell, 2014, 2022; Elling-Machartzki, 2017; Erikainen et al., 2022; Hargie et al., 2017; Jones et al., 2017; López-Cañada et al., 2021; Teti et al., 2020). For instance, Jones et al. (2017) showed that young trans adult participants were insufficiently

active and avoided engaging in LTPAS for different reasons, such as inadequate changing-room facilities, body dissatisfaction and fear of being unmasked. Body dissatisfaction is one of the main reasons that prevent trans people from getting involved in LTPAS (Caudwell, 2014, 2022; Elling-Machartzki, 2017; Erikainen et al., 2022; Hargie et al., 2017). Considering that the present paper focuses on research motives behind participation (rather than amotivation or non-participation), body satisfaction and gender congruence were found to be the motives for engaging in LTPAS (Jones et al., 2017), especially among transgender men, whose primary motive is body image (Teti et al., 2020). Moreover, health benefits also appear as a motive linked to LTPAS participation that reinforce or mitigate the side effects of hormone treatment (Elling-Machartzki, 2017; López-Cañada et al., 2021).

The complexity involved in studying trans people's motives for LTPAS participation requires a combination of the self-determination and transgender theories. Transgender theory emerged to provide understanding to transgender diversity and experiences that the queer, feminist and postmodern theories were unable to embrace (Roen, 2001). This is due to the lack of attention to the variety of lived realities of different groups of trans people, a deficiency on an active embodiment construction, and an absent focus on the social structure of (trans)gender. Transgender is understood, from the new theory, as an umbrella term that encompass a wide diversity of gender identities and expressions (i.e. transsexual, queer, gender diverse, nonbinary, agender, bigender, genderfluid, genderless, polygender, two spirit). Gender transition is conceptualized as a lifelong and complex process involved in the social interactions of daily life held in the negotiations of gender (Elling-Machartzki, 2017). Transgender theory integrates identities, lived experiences and embodiment within social practices and structures, considering their empowerment in alliances with other groups and communities (Nagoshi & Brzuzy, 2010; Nagoshi et al., 2023). In the context of LTPAS, the embodiment and trans people's experiences of pleasant and empowering instead of unpleasant

and disempowering experiences are particularly important (Barras & Frith, 2023; Elling-Machartzki, 2017). Barras and Frith (2023) highlight the role of gender euphoria feelings in the driving forces in LTPAS for transgender-affirming experiences, and not only the predominant feelings of gender dysphoria linked to discrimination and transnegativity. Elling-Machartzki (2017) emphasizes the role LTPAS play as technologies of the self for trans people, helping them to achieve their gendered embodied identities.

Against this backdrop, the general aim of this paper is to provide a wide understanding of trans persons' motives for participating in LTPAS through a mixed-method design driven by a combination of the self-determination theory and the transgender theory. Its specific purpose is thus two-fold: firstly, to identify Spanish trans persons' motives for LTPAS participation after GD, according to gender, age, and possible hormone treatment through a survey study; secondly, to go deeper into the circumstances and meanings which underpin trans people's motives for participation through a qualitative approach.

Method

Design

This study is a part of a three-year research project, carried out between 2012 and 2015. Participation of Spanish trans individuals in LTPAS was studied by means of an explanatory sequential mixed-method design (Creswell & Plano, 2011) in which qualitative data are used to provide a detailed explanation and to further illuminate the nuances revealed by the quantitative data. It is therefore a mixed-methods design with a rationale characterized by a complementary quantitative-qualitative connection by which empirically identified participation motives help to allocate the deductive exploration of circumstances and meanings, as well as the new ones obtained inductively that affect trans persons' participation in LTPAS.

Although both methodologies respond to different ontologies, rigor can be provided by connecting big quantitative data with deep qualitative data. This is possible because the small qualitative group shares the same characteristics as the big quantitative group, according to Collins and Evans (2017), since the second small sample is obtained from the first big sample. This type of mixed-method study therefore stresses what continues ontologically from the quantitative to the qualitative phase.

Participants

The participants were recruited from transgender sections of lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender (LGBT) collectives, Hospital Gender Identity Units, and through the snowball sampling procedure, a strategy suitable for finding participants from hidden and marginal populations (see Devís-Devís et al., 2017). A total of 212 trans people aged 10 to 62 years from different Spanish regions finally participated voluntarily in the quantitative phase. We included in the analysis only those participants who mentioned their participation in LTPAS after the GD ($n= 155$ transgender individuals; $M_{(age)}= 30.2$, $dt=9.8$; Spanish=92.6%, Other nationalities=7.4%) because the reasons for participation might have a greater impact and be more readily expressed once their gender became known (see Table 1). The participants' gender identity was identified through an open question. To be consistent with the purposes of the paper and the participants' different identities, the sample was grouped using various labels according to their self-determined gender: 'TM' gathers 'trans men,' 'men,' and 'boys;' 'TW' encompasses 'women,' 'trans women,' and 'girls'; and non-conforming binary gender participants, 'NBG', who self-identified as 'trans,' 'person' and 'queer.'

[Table 1 near here]

Of those who voluntarily agreed to participate in the subsequent qualitative phase, 43 trans persons (21 TW, 17 TM, and 5 NBG) between 15 and 62 years of age were interviewed

to get further insights into their personal lives, schooling, and the sociocultural aspects involved in their LTPAS engagement. Those in this phase were selected according to some features such as gender identity, age, and hormone treatment.

Procedures

The quantitative phase surveys were administrated face-to-face following a protocol designed by the research team. The surveys were anonymous, but to ensure data quality, they were administered face-to-face with a team member present to address any potential questions from the participants. On average, it took 20 minutes to answer the 43 items. The surveys were distributed in Spanish (although the results were subsequently translated for publication into English with the help of a native English speaker). A 5-point Likert scale of between 1 (strongly disagree) and 5 (strongly agree) was used to measure the motives of trans persons' LTPAS participation. The items on frequency, type, motives and organization of LTPAS were based on the study by García and Llopis (2011), adding three additional items focusing on the motives of trans population (“to reaffirm my gender identity,” “to increase my musculature,” “medical prescription”). The data collected were filtered to detect possible errors by individually analyzing non-valid or inconsistent responses and the aggregate behavior of some variables. To refine the questionnaire, avoid misunderstandings and, of special importance, agree on possible answers to the gender identity of participants, a pilot test was performed on 12 trans persons from an LGBT association. This aided in refining the gender labels used in the survey and in the process of removing, rephrasing, and reorganizing some of its questions. At the end of the survey, some space was provided to add any extra information the participants deemed relevant.

Qualitative data were gathered through individual semi-structured interviews that lasted between 45 minutes and 1 hour. The purpose of the interview was first explained, followed by

our relationship with the university and the aims of the research project, and then an agreement was made to meet for an interview at the participants' convenience. The interviewers answered any further doubts. All the interviews were recorded, fully transcribed verbatim, and returned to the participants, who were asked for their explicit agreement to use them as data in the study.

Data analysis

The variables included in the quantitative phase of the study were: (a) age; (b) gender identity; (c) LTPAS participation motives after GD; and (d) hormone treatment. A descriptive analysis based on the motive percentages was recodified in two categories: 1-3 disagreement or indifference; and 4-5 agreement. The relationships among the motives were identified by correlational analyses (Spearman's Rho). Group differences in the re-codified motives variable were analyzed by the Chi-square tests of independence ($p < .05$). When Chi-square tests were applied to variables with three comparison groups (gender identity and groups of age), the corrected standardized residuals (± 1.96) were calculated to establish in which categories significant differences emerged. One of the assumptions of the Chi-square test is that no more than 20% of the cells have frequencies below 5. When this assumption was violated, Fisher's exact test was applied. To determine the effect size of the Chi-square analyses, Cramer's V coefficient was used as a measure of the strength of the association, where ≥ 0.1 , ≥ 0.3 , and ≥ 0.5 represent a weak, moderate, or strong association respectively. SPSS v. 22.0 statistical software was used for coding and analyzing the data.

The qualitative analysis aimed to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the motives. The two members of the research team that collected the qualitative data were also responsible for coding them. The units of analysis consisted of complete sentences and meaningful segments transcribed from the thoughts expressed by transgender individuals

regarding their motivations for participating in LTPAS. We employed a codebook approach for thematic analysis, in accordance with the guidelines outlined by Braun and Clarke (2021), with the motives obtained in the previous quantitative phase, deducing categories from it. However, we remained open to new categories through the inductive analysis until we reached the point of analytical saturation. Throughout this analytical process, we ultimately identified two dominant key themes: "intrinsic" and "extrinsic" motives, which effectively connected the motives identified in the quantitative phase with the interpretations provided by the participants regarding their motivations for LTPAS participation.

Ethical concerns

All the materials and procedures used in the research project were approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of Valencia (code: H1328112240014). The survey respected the self-defined trans people's gender identities and random pseudonyms were assigned to participants to guarantee their anonymity and privacy. Informed consent forms authorizing the research team to publish the data obtained from the study were signed by adult participants or by the parents or guardians of those under 18 years of age with their prior consent. The surveys and informed consent forms were kept separately and the data were entered in a database for their subsequent statistical analysis. During the qualitative phase the researchers updated the informed consent at the beginning of the interviews.

A significant concern on the appropriate age to gather informed consent with minors led us to follow the recommendation by Gibson et al. (2011), who advise evaluating the maturity and capacity of participants as the data collection process unfolds. The role of parents in granting consent for their children's participation was also a subject of debate among the research team, as well as the possibility of interviewing minors who had not publicly disclosed their gender identity (even to their parents) but were willing to participate. In the end, consent

was provided by minors in collaboration with their parents, who were present when they were interviewed and in general were supportive of their children.

Beyond these considerations, we also faced the ethical challenges and specific concerns involved in research on the trans population. As cisgender researchers, we define ourselves as *cisgender allies* (Landi et al., 2020). Despite being sensitive to social justice for trans persons, we were aware of the impossibility of completely avoiding operating within some set of (cisnormative) assumptions (Hammersley, 2015). For this reason, we attempted to analyze ourselves critically to create the necessary epistemological vigilance with ourselves and the participants to reduce the influence of our cultural background and hegemonic position in the research process.

Results

Quantitative results

Among the trans people who participated in LTPAS after GD (N=155), “to do physical exercise” was the most frequently reported motive (84.2%), followed by “to keep and improve health” (75.5%), “to enjoy doing sport” (74.5%) and “fun and entertainment” (73.5%). The least frequent motives were “medical prescription” (23.1%), and “to enjoy competing” (23.1%) (see Figure 1 for all the motives).

[Figure 1 near here]

Spearman’s non-parametric correlation analysis of LTPAS participation motives after GD revealed several significant relationships (all positive) (Table 2). The strongest correlations found among trans participants in LTPAS were between the motives “to keep and improve health” and “keeping in good shape” (two motives with external driven forces), as well as between “being with friends” and “for fun and entertainment” (a motive with external and another one with internal impelled forces). In addition, other significant correlations were

found between the motive “to do physical exercise” and the following: “to enjoy doing sport,” “keeping in good shape,” “to keep and improve health” and “to increase my musculature” (mainly motives by externally driven forces).

[Table 2 near here]

[Table 3 near here]

The group differences in trans persons’ participation motives can be seen in Table 3. By gender identity, the overall values indicated that “to do physical exercise” (75.4%), “to keep and improve health” (69.5%), “keeping in good shape” (67.2%) and “fun and entertainment” (67.2%) were the most frequently cited motives by TW. For TM, “to do physical exercise” (91.6%), “to enjoy doing sport” (86.7%), “to keep and improve health” (82.5%) and “fun and entertainment” (79.7%) were the main motives reported. For NBG persons, “to do physical exercise” (85.7%) and “to enjoy doing sport” (71.4%) were the most frequently reported motives for LTPAS participation. There were significant differences ($p<.05$) in “to reaffirm my gender identity,” “to do physical exercise,” “to enjoy doing sport,” and “to increase my musculature” motives, where TM and NBG showed higher values than TW.

By age group, “fun and entertainment” was the motive most frequently stated by the ≤ 20 year-old group (84.6%), followed by “to enjoy doing sport” (73.1%) and “to do physical exercise” (73.1%). For the 21-39 year-old group, "to do physical exercise" (89.2%), "to enjoy doing sport" (79.3%), "to keep and improve health" (76.9%) were the most frequently used. "To do physical exercise" (86.2%), "to keep and improve health" (84.6%), and "keeping in good shape" (70.4%) were most often cited by the ≥ 40 year-old group. Significant differences ($p<.05$) were found in “to increase my musculature,” in which the 21-39 year-old group showed higher values than the ≥ 40 year-old group.

By hormone treatment, significant differences ($p < .05$) were found between the motives “to do physical exercise” and “to increase my musculature,” in which trans people receiving hormone treatment obtained higher values than those who were not.

Qualitative results

Understanding intrinsic motives

“Enjoyment” was one of the main motives indicated by trans people for LTPAS participation, with an intrinsic meaning since it was driven by their internal forces. The interviewees, especially TM and NBG, highlighted their enthusiasm for and satisfaction with LTPAS:

I have always ... I’ve always liked it [practicing football] so much, that is, I’ve given myself to it [football]... it is something I love to play and also to watch (Calixto, TM-24 years old).

I like to do it [physical exercise], so when I do it, I’m comfortable, I’m relaxed, I feel good, I’m shinier, I’m happy ... (Jorge, TM-42 years old).

I always liked sports, I’ve always been very active. I was quite fit, and played football all the time when I was a child. I’ve always been keen on sports [...] sport makes me feel good. (Alex, NBG-32 years old).

Trans persons also referred to “fun and entertainment” as a motive to engage in LTPAS, especially when they can choose the activities:

When I could choose what I really wanted to do was when I started to like doing sport [...] I do it for fun especially, because, I tell you, I’ve always done it for fun, even now, as an adult (Hanna, TW-27 years old).

It is also obviously a part of entertainment, “Let's go for a ride on the bike!” [...] That is, it's fun, leisure, isn't it? And then, there are other times when maybe we're going to play basketball for a while. That's also entertainment, I enjoy it (Daniel, TM-33 years old).

Some motives on LTPAS are related more to the “exercise exertion and self-satisfaction” to complete an activity than with its actual outcome. For instance, Carolina (TW-40 years old) said she enjoyed the challenge of finishing a strenuous choreography routine as a very physical pleasure, even when her performance was not up to scratch:

That feeling of exertion ... I think that sport has that, sport forces you to push yourself in a very short of time. [...] Sport helps me to make an effort in an hour, and when you are in the shower, you say “I did a good workout.” [...] I'm a bit clumsy, but ... I did it! [...] I'm still capable of doing what's good for me even if I have to struggle. Then, I feel good.

Some trans persons realized that “fulfillment and self-improvement” are a dimension of LTPAS participation which can be transferred to their lives, as Naím and Lucas stated:

For me, sport means personal self-improvement. To see that you can do something... you can also do other things better in life. That is, if I was able to run many kilometers ... or to play that game and I did it well or won a game of bowls while the rest of the people were against me ... things like that if you see that you can improve yourself in sport, you feel that you do the same in other things (Naím, TM-20 years old).

You feel better doing... when you say “wow! today I have run a lot, so another day I'll get to the next tree, at the bottom, and the next day I will get even farther.” It is like personal self-improvement, then all this motivates you so much to keep on going, to say “wow! now I can do more,” and that cheers you up (Lucas, TM-23 years old).

According to Lucas' last quotation, his experience of personal "fulfillment" in LTPAS became a motive to go on exercising, confirming the intrinsic meaning of this LTPAS motive.

Understanding extrinsic motives

Trans individuals' primary external motivations for participating in LTPAS were mainly linked to the aspiration of achieving gender-related bodily changes that align with cis-heteronormative standards. Most trans participants, both TM, TW, and NBG noted that they could build up a *desired* body through physical activity and sport. Qualitative data show that expected "body changes" through LTPAS are targeted in specific parts of the body and are drastically different between TW and TM. In particular, TW were motivated to tone up their legs and gluteus, as Inma explains (TW-19 years old):

The sport I do is from the waist down, mostly to strengthen, burn fat and have...I mean, larger hips [...] I would like to increase my glutes and to reduce ... well, I would like to have a slimmer back.

Contrariwise, most TM looked "to increase their muscularity," especially the upper extremities. For instance, Leónidas (TM-24 years old) stated, "I'm looking for a bit of [arm] volume, more than anything because I want to get broader, to have bigger muscles." Iker (NBG-28 years old) referred to bodybuilding from a more utilitarian perspective: "for me, the gym is a way to tone up the muscles because I work so much, and I have a big bike ... I need to have good muscle tone."

The determination to achieve a body in accordance with their gender expectations shows the importance of LTPAS participation in reaffirming trans persons' identities. Their desired outcomes often match with the dominant body gender stereotypes since LTPAS participation becomes a means of acquiring a feminine *or* masculine "appearance and body image," as observed in these quotations:

What I have observed in my body with exercise is that you are shaping your figure, you look more attractive, and they see you as more attractive. Although you continue to feminize your body with hormones and keep reducing your testosterone in the body with hormone treatment, the body needs a little push to be as it should be! (Marisa, TW-42 years old).

And of course, I do want to have a masculine body shape, it is part of what ... let's say of the desire for what I am. [...] I want musculature, that is, to make a mannish figure. (Fernando, TM-48 years old).

However, Iker (NBG-28 years old), when referring to “in the middle” in the following quote, showed interest in queering a strong body rather in between a feminine and masculine appearance:

There are also aesthetic and desire issues, [...] I am getting stronger now. [...] although I am in the middle [as queer], I would like to perform a little more masculine, if we understand masculinity as a little more muscle, strength, and so on...

As observed in the quantitative phase, another noteworthy motive for participating in LTPAS was “maintaining and enhancing health.” TM, TW and NBG participants were conscious of the health benefits of practicing sport, as indicated in the following quotations:

[I do exercise] to have a healthy body, and... now, more than anything it is a matter of health and cardiovascular and muscular improvement. [...] It's a matter of health. (Santi, TM-54 years old).

... moderate exercise every day is good for my health. I have cholesterol and exercise is good for [reducing] cholesterol. (Rebeca, TW-40 years old).

When you do sports everything goes well, you eat well, the intestinal motility works better, the mind works better ... that's it. (Iker, NBG-28 years old).

The last quotation shows how participants in this study not only pointed out extrinsic meanings associated with improved physical health, but also psychological improvements. Most interviewees found LTPAS to be a method of “escaping” or forgetting their daily routine and problems:

It’s like an escape, when I go cycling I disconnect from everything, which brings me great mental relaxation. I enjoy it a lot. Sometimes, if I'm angry or upset or anxious about something, I ride the bike and when I go out... it's an escape, it's a way out, it's a relief. (Daniel, TM-33 years old).

For example, swimming helps me to escape, it helps me a lot. [...] For me, swimming has always been a liberation and my favorite sport forever and ever (laughs), and the truth is that... I don’t know, it’s like a relief, it’s like ‘an oasis in the desert.’ If you’ve had a shit of a day you can say, well I'm going to swim, to escape... (Almudena, TW-26 years old).

As it was a period when I was having a hard time, sports allowed me to escape a little bit from all the problems I had and, since I felt good, I continued practicing [...] It is good for me because it helps to relax my mind. (Carmela, NBG-38 years old).

“Social relationships” were also important motives for trans persons to engage in LTPAS. Going out and making friends is important because “belonging to a group and socializing with people” is part of the social health benefits, as stated in the next quotations:

So, I like to go to the gym not only to lift weights and improve my figure, shaping my body, right? But also because it is a way of being in contact with other people who have similar interests, regardless of whether they are boys or girls. (Santi, TM-54 years old).

[Sport] helped me to get away from the street, especially swimming. When I joined the swimming team, I did it mainly to go out, to meet people, people similar to me [...] I did

it well with social relationships, in fact, right now they are the only people I can consider as friends. (Marisa, TW-42 years old).

I also see sport as a space to share, because meeting people and working in teams, it seems a way to meet people and it's cool. (Iker, NBG-28 years old).

Discussion

The combination of the self-determination theory and the transgender theory through a mixed method study provides a deep understanding of trans people motives for participating in LTPAS. The self-determination theory not only contributes, according to Ryan and Deci (2000), to focus our research interest on the motives instead of amotivation or reasons for not participation, but also provides a conceptual body of knowledge for establishing comparisons and understanding the driving forces impelling trans people to engage in LTPAS. The transgender theory, as recently emphasised by Nagoshi et al. (2023), helps to understand the role that gender identity and embodiment play in the motives of participation. Additionally, it sheds light on the potential diversity in the motives of trans people compared to the general population.

The most popular trans persons' motives for LTPAS participation identified in the quantitative results are, in this order: "to do physical exercise," "to keep and improve health," "to enjoy doing sport" and "fun and entertainment." These four motives are similar to the main ones identified in studies on the general Spanish population for LTPAS participation (Ministry of Education, Culture & Sport, 2015). The first motive for the general population ("to do physical exercise") was also the most reported in the TM, TW and NBG groups. Interestingly, the least important motive in the study ("to enjoy competing") is also the least reported motive in the general population as well as in a study on a large sample of Spanish adolescents (Martínez et al., 2012). These similarities indicate that, from an epidemiological

point of view, there is no great difference between trans people's motives for LTPAS and those of the general Spanish population at the time of data gathering. They also suggest that the Spanish trans population was losing interest at that moment in organized sporting practices in favor of leisure activities (García & Llopis, 2011; Martínez et al., 2012; Ministry of Education, Culture & Sport, 2015).

The motive “to increase musculature” is in sixth place in the quantitative results, but its relevant presence in the qualitative results suggests that this motive plays an important role, although more important among the TM and NBG than the TW in the sample. This reflects the importance of body physicality linked to the TM's interest in bodybuilding as a gender-making strategy (Elling-Machartzki, 2017; Jones et al., 2017; Schrock et al., 2005). The quantitative findings also show that trans people undergoing hormone treatment are more motivated to increase their musculature through LTPAS participation, perhaps because LTPAS may accelerate this treatment, particularly in bodybuilding in TM (Elling-Machartzki, 2017; Jones et al., 2017; López-Cañada et al., 2021).

The young trans adults (≤ 20 and 21-39 years old) are also more motivated towards LTPAS “to increase their musculature” than older trans people (≥ 40 years old), according to the quantitative results, as found in previous research on the general population (Brudzynski & Ebben, 2010). This also suggests that “appearance and body image” are important reasons for participating in LTPAS, both among transgender and young adults in the general population. Noteworthy, the average age of GD in the current study is 22 years, a moment when many trans persons undergo gender-affirming hormone treatment (Ettner et al., 2007). This treatment can either slow or enhance certain secondary sex characteristics which fit in with cultural ideals of gendered body appearance in Western society (Grogan, 2016). Thence, physical appearance and body image can be seen as driving forces to align LTPAS with the

purpose of young transgender adults to being publicly recognized and accepted in society (Barras & Frith, 2023; Elling-Machartzki, 2017).

The qualitative results contribute to a deeper understanding of intrinsic and extrinsic motives. In both the quantitative and qualitative results, participants consistently mention “enjoy/enjoyment” and “fun and entertainment” as intrinsic motives for engaging in LTPAS. However, the qualitative findings reveal an additional intrinsic motive, “exercise exertion and self-satisfaction,” (which is not related with those identified in the quantitative analysis) that shows the significance of embodied pleasure in the involvement of transgender individuals in sports and physical exercise (Barras & Frith, 2023).

A wider and more explicit understanding of the extrinsic motives can also be found in the qualitative results of this study. For instance, the motive “maintaining and enhancing health” shows the importance of LTPAS in strengthening or mitigating the effects of hormone treatment (López-Cañada et al., 2021), and also stresses the relevance of the psychological benefits of LTPAS. In this regard, its attraction as a way of escaping from discrimination and suffering in society could be of particular importance for trans people compared with the general population (Bouman et al., 2017; Millet et al., 2017). The qualitative results also highlight the importance of social relations as a motive for LTPAS that among trans people becomes a form of social acceptance, while exclusion or hindrances are associated with the rejection of their gender identities (Devís-Devís et al., 2018).

Nevertheless, the extrinsic character of these motives sometimes reveals connections with the socio-emotional pleasures of socialization and relationships with intrinsically associated motives of pleasure. This is also found regarding the “appearance and body image” motive in the qualitative results, providing evidence on how trans participants rely on specific outcomes to re-create a gendered body and reproducing masculine and feminine stereotypes.

TM are not the only group who want to increase their musculature; TW tone up or slim particular body targets (hips, legs). NBG participants are also interested in their physical appearance but more for aesthetic reasons than for reproducing gender stereotypes. This shows that extrinsic motives also enclose gender euphoria feelings of positive emotion and joyful intrinsic motives because of their gender-affirming embodiment (Barras & Frith, 2023; Elling-Machartzki, 2017). This connection between extrinsic and intrinsic motives is also found in the positive correlations between some intrinsic/extrinsic motives (e.g., “to enjoy doing sport” and “to increase my musculature”) inasmuch as they frequently appear in combination for people’s involvement in LTPAS in everyday life (Coakley, 2012).

The implications of these results must be placed within trans people’s particular expectations and problems with gender binary system in LTPAS contexts. For those trans persons who aim to be publicly recognized and accepted in society as a man *or* woman, the motive to improve his/her appearance expresses a wish to conform his/her body to binary stereotypes. However, being recognized as a man or woman is not (or should not be) a requisite to enjoy LTPAS. Moreover, as transgender theory suggests, not all trans persons are willing or able to undergo the gender affirmative surgery dictated by the gender binary system (Nagoshi et al. 2023). In this regard, the results show that LTPAS participation makes personal enjoyment and social interaction possible and so can contribute to all trans persons’ entertainment and wellbeing, including NBG persons. LTPAS can thus become an important domain for the inclusion, dialogue and encounters between diverse and heterogeneous bodies.

These two apparently contradictory functions (whether or not to conform with the gender binary system) reveal the multiple possibilities of LTPAS to respond to different trans identities, and also the important challenge of considering the particular (and potentially different) motives for trans people. The social acceptance of trans persons’ gender identities in binary LTPAS contexts can reinforce the transition process, which often entails considerable

body changes that can easily be noticed (and rejected) in these contexts. However, LTPAS contexts cannot simply act as a sort of means or token for trans persons (non)conforming to gender binary. They can and must also provide a favorable social environment to gender-diverse persons, including those who reject binary gender identities. Thus, trans people with non-binary gender identities and bodies should be welcome in LTPAS practices and spaces, where safe and reassuring experiences should be endured for everybody.

Examining LTPAS practices and experiences of trans people through the lenses of self-determination and transgender theories can also contribute to their refinement and enrichment. In general, literature calling upon self-determination theory assumes that relationships between intrinsic and extrinsic motives are linked to binary gender conceptions. Therefore, understanding how different types of motives are combined and interact among self-affirming trans people may help refine the relations between of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation from a gender diversity perspective, rather than the predominant binary one. On the other hand, the use of qualitative methods highlights how content-specific insights, such as type of sport, previous experiences, or the need for body exposure, can be integrated into transgender theory, providing a more accurate and nuanced understanding of LTPAS experiences of trans people. Incorporating these elements can expand both theories not only in connection with the experiences of trans persons but also to the general population in the realms of LTPAS.

Some of the limitations of this study should be pointed out. Firstly, it was not possible to establish a representative sample (quantitative phase) due to the lack of a register or reliable estimation of the number of trans people in Spain. Even so, the final study sample was the most widely used in the Spanish context and one of the most extensive in a mixed-method study on trans persons. Secondly, the reduced number of NBG participants could have affected our quantitative and qualitative results, probably due to the recruitment process, based on LGBT collectives and Hospital Gender Identity Units. Thirdly, our discussion relies

heavily on other studies on the general population, as the lack of similar studies on trans persons makes it difficult to focus on the motives of this vulnerable group, while the traditional binary gender division of studies on the general population influences the potential comparison of the results. Fourthly, the timeline of data collection can be a potential limitation of the study, particularly considering the extensive literature and debates surrounding the participation of trans people in high-performance sports over the past decade. However, our focus lies within the realm of LTPAS – a domain that should ideally be uncontroversial, given that physical activity is a fundamental human right. Moreover, given the mixed methods approach employed in our study, we believe that our findings are robust and merit sharing with the academic community.

Finally, while this research is centered on Spain, it is equally crucial to gain insights into participation motives in other European and Western countries, as well as other cultural and geographic settings. In this regard, it becomes particularly important to consider how legal frameworks for recognizing gender identities might also impact the motives for participating in LTPA.

Conclusions

To our knowledge, this is the first empirical approach specifically focused on trans persons' motives for participating in LTPAS according to their self-identified gender (TM, TW and NBG). It is also one of the first to follow a mixed-methods design to explore motives, combining the self-determination theory and the transgender theory. This work balances the general understanding underlying previous studies on motives, which do not consider the fact of being a trans person as an issue of concern, enriching the scope of the self-determination theory. Moreover, combining it with transgender theory through a mixed methods design we

address the complexities in studying LTPAS motives in the transgender population in comparison with the general population.

The present findings show that “to do physical exercise,” “to keep and improve health,” “to enjoy doing sport” and “fun and entertainment” are the four most important motives for trans persons to practice LTPAS while the least important is “to enjoy competing.” It is central to reinforce the fact that both trans persons and the Spanish general population present similar reasons for participating in LTPAS and both populations are losing interest in sporting practices in favor of exercise activities.

The quantitative and qualitative results show similar intrinsic motives such as “enjoyment” and “fun and entertainment.” Additionally, motives linked to the pleasure of body exertion and the satisfaction of carrying out an activity by oneself were identified in the qualitative phase. Similar extrinsic motives can also be found for health and socialization, as well as “muscular motives,” although the qualitative results especially emphasize the “health and body motives” that help to affirm their gender identity. Many trans persons engage in LTPAS to strengthen or mitigate the effects of hormone treatment, and/or use it as an escape valve for their everyday problems. The motives related to “appearance and body image” refer to reproducing gender among TM and TW, and aesthetic purposes among the NBG participants.

The relationships between intrinsic and extrinsic motives emerge in the correlations established in the quantitative analysis (e.g., “to enjoy doing sport” and “to increase my musculature”) and also the qualitative analysis (e.g., physical appearance motive and gender euphoria feelings). This is because both types of motives frequently appear combined and, also, linked to the participants’ gender-affirming embodiment.

The quantitative and qualitative results of this study will contribute to sensitizing health and physical activity professionals, policy makers and society in general for increasing trans persons' involvement and satisfactory experiences in LTPAS participation. Hopefully, these findings will also help to improve trans persons' opportunities for well-being and social involvement.

Declaration of interest statement

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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Table 1. Descriptive characteristics of the sample.

	Final sample <i>n</i> =155 (100%)
Gender Identity	
TW	64 (41.3)
TM	84 (54.2)
NBG	7 (4.5)
Age [mean(SD)]	30.24 (9.68)
<20 years	26 (17.2)
21-39 years	95 (62.9)
≥40 years	30 (19.9)
Hormone treatment	104 (67.1)

TW: Trans women; TM: Trans men; NBG: Non-conforming binary gender persons. SD: Standard deviation.

Table 2. Spearman's Rho correlation matrix between participation motives.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1.To reaffirm my gender identity	–									
2.For fun and entertainment	.01	–								
3.Being with friends	.03	.52**	–							
4.To do physical exercise	-.01	.39**	.19*	–						
5.To enjoy doing sport	.02	.31**	.21*	.48**	–					
6.Keeping in good shape	.23*	.12	.009	.46**	.35**	–				
7.Escaping	.004	.21**	.23**	.19*	.14	.32**	–			
8.To keep and improve health	.09	.14	.15	.50**	.34**	.55**	.23*	–		
9.To enjoy competing	.14	.07	.20*	.03	.26**	.01	.14	.09	–	
10.To increase my musculature	.36**	.18*	.07	.34**	.44**	.21*	.002	.21*	.31**	–
11.Medical prescription	.16	.02	.25**	-.04	-.08	.01	.01	.15	.09	-.06

** $p < .01$, * $p < .05$

Table 3. Motives of participation in leisure-time physical activity and sport by gender identity, age group and hormone treatment.

		To reaffirm my gender identity	For fun and entertainment	Being with friends	To do physical exercise	To enjoy doing sport	Keeping in good shape	Escaping	To keep and improve health	To enjoy competing	To increase my musculature	Medical prescription	
Gender Identity	Trans women	n	59	61	56	61	58	58	58	59	58	58	
		n(%)	11(18.6)	41(67.2)	25(44.6)	46(75.4)	34(58.6)	39(67.2)	30(51.7)	41(69.5)	9(15.5)	6(10.3)	13(22.4)
	Trans men	n	81	79	78	83	83	81	76	80	77	82	77
		n(%)	35(43.2)	63(79.7)	33(42.3)	76(91.6)	72(86.7)	58(71.6)	34(44.7)	66(82.5)	22(28.6)	64(78.0)	20(26)
	Non-conforming binary gender persons	n	7	7	6	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
		n(%)	2(28.6)	4(57.1)	3(50.0)	6(85.7)	5(71.4)	3(42.9)	3(42.9)	4(57.1)	2(28.6)	3(42.9)	0(0.0)
		<i>Chi-square</i>	9.23^f	3.27	0.33 ^f	6.04	13.3	2.34	0.875 ^f	3.99	3.14	66.45^f	2.40
	<i>p</i>	.009	.195	.877	.049	.001	.316	.661	.136	.208	<.001	.301	
	<i>Cramer's V</i>	.24	.14	.04	.19	.29	.12	.07	.16	.14	.64	.13	
Groups of age	≤20	n	24	26	24	26	26	26	24	26	25	23	
		n(%)	11(45.8)	22(84.6)	10(41.7)	19(73.1)	19(73.1)	17(65.4)	11(45.8)	16(61.5)	8(32)	13(50)	5(21.7)
	21-39	n	92	93	89	93	92	90	89	91	90	91	91
		n(%)	30(32.6)	68(73.1)	43(48.3)	83(89.2)	73(79.3)	62(68.9)	40(44.9)	70(76.9)	20(22.2)	51(56)	20(22)
	≥40	n	28	25	24	29	28	27	25	26	25	28	25
		n(%)	6(21.4)	17(68)	8(33.3)	25(86.2)	18(64.3)	19(70.4)	16(64)	22(84.6)	4(16)	8(28.6)	7(28)
		<i>Chi-square</i>	3.50	2.03	1.81	4.36	2.71	0.167	2.92	4.01	1.87	6.46	0.427
	<i>p</i>	.174	.361	.404	.113	.258	.920	.232	.135	.392	.039	.808	
	<i>Cramer's V</i>	.15	.12	.11	.17	.13	.03	.14	.16	.11	.21	.055	
Hormone treatment	Receiving	n	101	101	97	102	101	100	96	100	98	98	
		n(%)	34(33.7)	77(76.2)	43(44.3)	93(91.2)	79(78.2)	73(73)	48(50)	80(80)	22(22.4)	58(58.6)	22(22.4)
	Not receiving	n	47	47	44	50	48	47	46	47	45	49	45
		n(%)	14(29.2)	31(66)	18(40.9)	35(70)	32(66.7)	27(57.4)	19(41.3)	31(66)	11(24.4)	15(30.6)	11(24.4)
		<i>Chi-square</i>	0.220	1.719	0.144	11.316	2.28	3.55	0.944	3.409	0.069	10.261	0.069
		<i>p</i>	.639	.190	.704	.001	.131	.059	.331	.065	.793	.001	.793
		<i>Cramer's V</i>	.03	.10	.03	.27	.12	.15	0.08	.15	.02	.26	.02

Chi-square and Fisher's exact test where $p < 0.05$ are marked in bold lettering. ^f: Fisher's exact test was conducted.

Figure 1. Motives of participation in leisure-time physical activity and sport (%).

